

REVIEW ON ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGIES IN A PERSPECTIVE OF HALOPHYTE-BASED BIO-REFINERY

Sanketkumar Raval^{1*}, Tutku Taşçı Çilak¹, Sylvia Fasse¹, Mette Hedegaard Thomsen², Axel Gottschalk¹

¹ Department of Process Engineering, University of Applied Sciences Bremerhaven, Germany
An der Karlstadt 8, 27568, Bremerhaven

² Department for Energy Technology, Aalborg University – Esbjerg Campus, Denmark
Niels Bohrs Vej 8, 6700 Esbjerg, Denmark

*Email address corresponding author: sraval@hs-bremerhaven.de

ABSTRACT: Currently, the most concerning situation of global warming, climate change and fossil resources depletion push us towards bio-based economy from fossil dependent economy. Acknowledging the fact of curbing the environmental burden, the environmental performance of the bio-based refinery should be assessed even though it is in the developmental phase. In that regard, the aim of this study is to provide outline of the methods to gauge environmental performance and their applicability. In addition, the research on valorisation of halophytes to value products and the development of commercial scale bio-refinery concepts are ongoing because of the potential of high value-added products that can be extracted from halophytes. In order to assess and compare the various processes or feedstocks options for particular products, a certain framework and tools are needed. This paper provides the highlights on those important aspects. The aim of this paper is to document the outcomes of literature review and methods that can be implemented for finding sustainable processes and also provides guidance in the selection of suitable indicators that complements the goal of assessment of bio-refinery concepts.

Keywords: Biorefinery, sustainability, life cycle assessment (LCA)

1 INTRODUCTION

The beginning of the 21st century is marked by global scarcity of water resources, environmental pollution and increased salinization of soil and water [1]. In that scenario, using salt-tolerant crops are one of the most important strategies to solve the problem of the salinity of land. Halophytes are plants naturally adapted to saline conditions and represent 2% of terrestrial plants. As defensive strategy to the environmental stress, this plant synthesizes secondary metabolites such as phenolic compounds with high antioxidant activity due to their redox properties. The economic interest for halophytes plants is steadily increasing; these plants show potential application in food industry, medicine or cosmetic due to their richness in fibres, essential oils and phenolic compounds [2]. Examples of such salt tolerated plants are *Salicornia europaea* and *Crithmum maritimum* which are typical halophyte plants of the Mediterranean coastline, Black Sea and Atlantic coasts growing up on maritime cliffs and sometimes in sand [3].

Since the extractives from halophytes have potential applications, the use of halophytes as a feedstock to biorefinery is evident [2]. Non-fossil resources for biochemical production comes with the challenges related to the environmental sustainability, that is why an investigation is required in terms of impacts from feedstock generation, production of process, end-of-life treatment of products etc. [4].

The current study undertakes a review of fundamental aspects of sustainable biorefining pathways and also focus on the methodological assessment of such systems. In that regard, the current report includes the details about basics of biorefinery, raw material and its products. The information related to the methodology of sustainable assessment and life cycle assessment of the system is also provided.

2 BASICS OF BIOREFINERY

2.1 Biorefinery classifications

In recent years, the focus is on the replacement of conventional biorefinery by implementation of bio-based refinery operations [5]. These steps will reduce the dependency on the consumption of conventional fuel for energy need [6]. The target of replacement of products from conventional sources is only possible when the alternative such as biofuels, bio-based chemicals etc. are available to the customer [7]. Generally, there are four classifications in which the biorefineries are differentiated in. 1. Based on type of raw material used (e.g. green biorefinery, lignocellulosic biorefinery, marine biorefinery) 2. Use of various technology (e.g. thermo-chemical process, biochemical conversion) 3. Status of technology (such as conventional technology, advanced biorefinery, 1st, 2nd and 3rd generation biorefinery) 4. Depending on the products generated (biobased chemicals, biogas, biochar, lignin platforms, sugar extractives) [8].

With regard to the process involved in the biorefinery, there are four main technical processes such as chemical process, thermochemical process, biochemical process, physical process are used [9]. In another perspective, the biorefinery concepts can be categorised based on biochemical platforms and thermochemical platforms. For example, the fermentation of sugars that are extracted from lignocellulosic biomass fall under the first category. The generated sugars are then converted to value products such as fuel or biochemicals. Whereas in the case of thermochemical platform, the processes such as pyrolysis and gasification are involved to generate products like syngas, biochar, heat and electricity [10]. In recent times, to achieve the environmentally viable and economically feasible process setups, several stages and operations are integrated in advanced biorefinery.

Concerning the treatment of lignocellulosic materials, such as wood, plants, grass, straws, agriculture wastes, lignocellulosic biorefinery offers products that can be produce at large scale [11]. In the contrary, green biorefinery that is focused on high value compounds, like

proteins, and biochemicals, are popular in northern European countries [12]. In this type of biorefinery, the cake and juice are separated at first place and then treated further for extracting products (e.g. Cellulose, starch, proteins, polyphenols etc) [12].

2.2 Raw materials and products

A wide range of feedstocks including energy crops are used in biorefinery [6]. For example, in the 1st generation of biorefineries, corn is used as raw material for the purpose of bioethanol production in north America [13]. Whereas in Brazil, soybean is subjected to production of biodiesel and sugarcane is used for bioethanol production [13]. The use of edible crop in the biorefinery have consequences on the feedstock market and also on the global output of crops to ensure the consistent supply of raw material [14].

Along with the availability of feedstock, the cost of cultivation is also important [15]. Generally, 40-60% of cost is allocated to raw materials for biorefinery [2]. That is why feedstock is important to optimize the production cost of bio-based products [2]. Furthermore, the consideration of chemical composition of biomass is very significant because it will have impact of type of products that are produced from biorefinery [16]. For examples, sugars that are separated from lignocellulosic biomass is further converted to succinic acid which is used in food and pharmaceutical industry [17]. Halophytes species such as *Salicornia europaea* and *Crithmum maritimum* can also be used as feedstock to extract the phenolic contents, flavonoid content and antioxidant compounds [18].

In case of products, the speciality biochemicals (flavours and fragrances, enzymes, succinic acid, essential amino acids, vitamins etc.) are in high demand in the market. The overall market growth is 10-20% per year [11]. A report on the estimation of the potential market of bio-based product in European Union is released by European commission taskforce in 2007 [19]. Global sales of bio-based chemicals was US\$77 billion where European Union contributed by 30% [19]. Similarly, the study done by International Energy Agency (IEA) has also estimated the high demand of biobased materials and has forecasted the high growth in future [20].

2.3 Biorefinery processes

The various process routes are followed for specific type of biorefinery. In a lignocellulosic biorefinery, the production process of bio-based products from raw material occurs in four major steps. 1. pre-treatment of biomass 2. hydrolysis 3. fermentation and 4. product recovery [21]

In order to break down the lignocellulosic molecules and convert it into reactive cellulosic intermediates, pre-treatment is the required [22]. Since the crystalline cellulose structure has the long chain of glucose linked with β -1,4 glycosidic linkage, which is difficult to break down, the pre-treatment is generally energy intensive process [23]. Usual composition of biomass includes 35-50% of cellulose, 23-35% of hemicellulose and 14-20% of lignin [6]. After pre-treatment, the fraction of cellulose increases up to 85% whereas hemicellulose and lignin reduces to 22% and 9%, respectively [24]. Afterwards, the cellulose is subjected to hydrolysis process where the cellulose is converted to glucose by enzymatic treatment or any other chemical method. In order to produce

ethanol from sugars, the fermentation process is the further step [22].

In the case of use of feedstock with high content of starch, hydrolysis is performed by adding glucoamylases, which produces sugars. Like lignocellulosic biorefinery, a fermentation is required to convert sugars into bioethanol and coproducts such as animal feed and fraction of proteins and fibres [16].

In case of use of green or lignified feedstock, extraction processes such as Soxhlet extraction, maceration and solvent extraction is applied which basically separate the extractives from biomass [18].

The pre-treatment of lignocellulosic biomass has an impact on the technical as well as economic performance of the overall process [25]. In case of organic solvent pre-treatment, catalyst is required which need to separate from product stream afterwards. In case of dilute sulphuric acid pre-treatment, generally it dissolves high fraction of hemicellulose whereas less lignin is dissolved. Since a high temperature is required in this process, it can further impact negatively on fermentation process. another pre-treatment of biomass is steam pre-treatment where impregnating agents are needed to improve the yield [26].

Since the presence of lignin in the biomass inhibits the process of enzymatic hydrolysis, removal of lignin at first place promotes the hydrolysis of biomass [27]. Moreover, separated lignin that contains 40% of heat content in biomass, can be used as source of heat [27]. Though lignin can be used as source of heat, because of having acid contaminations, the burning of lignin poses negative impact on sustainability of whole production process [28]. As lignin can be valorised to various bulk chemicals such as aromatic compounds, this approach adds new value chains in the bio-based chemical market and helps to reduce environmental burden arises from fossil-based chemicals [29]. A process that is used for separation cellulose and lignin is organosolv process where lignin is dissolved in solvent and further separated from other biomass compounds [30]. A list of potential lignin-based bio-chemicals is given by Holladay et al [31].

3 METHODOLOGY: SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF BIOREFINERY

3.1 Sustainability assessment framework

When assessing the environmental impacts and life cycle of biochemicals, a large variation in LCA studies is obvious. One of the key reasons is that each system is unique regarding the processes, feed stocks, products etc [32]. In addition to that, biorefinery consists of multiple material flows and it has multiple indicators involved that are necessary for decision making on environmental performance of processes and products [33]. For comparing biorefinery systems in detailed manner, an integrated framework of evaluation of alternatives is needed. In order to perform sustainability assessment of biorefinery, mainly three key aspects are considered. First is the feedstock generation, its availability and suitability for the biorefinery. Second is the processes involved in conversion of biomass into value products along with resources that are required for operations. Third is bio-based products production which is ultimately replace the usage of fossil-based chemicals. Thus, it has high impact on sustainability of biorefinery in terms of

environmental, economic and social performances. In addition to the biobased product production, the end-of-life scenario also should be included in life cycle assessment study (LCA) so that all possible environmental benefits or impacts can be uncovered [34].

3.2 Assessment tools

In order to perform the sustainability assessment of biorefinery, tools are required which can be categorised as monetary, biophysical and indicator tool. These tools can be operated independently as well as in an integrated manner depending on the complexity of system and aim of the study [35].

The monetary tools are used to compare the market price, economic modelling of system, transfer of benefits as well as the aggregation of cost benefits analysis and sustainability assessment modelling [36] [37]. These tools are helpful for cost optimization and comparison of various products [38]. In order to estimate the ecological footprints, energy balance or energy analysis based on the material flows of the system, the biophysical tools are useful [39]. Key benefit of this tool is that it quantifies the flow of materials under transformation (feedstock to final products) and correlate alternatives in socio-economic and environmental paradigm [39]. The indicator-based tools perform the task of defining and assigning the composite indicators and also evaluate the alternatives based on multi-criteria assessment. The indicator tool is used to identify the most impactful stage of biomass conversion based on socio-economic and environmental category. Despite the advantages of these tools, there is a challenge of availability of data required for assessment throughout the product value chains [40].

4 IMPORTANT CONSIDERATION FOR LCA

4.1 Inclusion of all components and related environmental impact

The research on various existing LCA studies done by Ögmundarson et al. [4] concluded on the most relevant impact category. It is found that, during feedstock production and energy and water use in processes, most relevant impact category are global warming, land and water use, eutrophication and ecotoxicity. From the study, it is found that the land use for farming (feedstock production) is most relevant for LCA study, since land use impact category represents the change in use of land from the expansion of cropland because of the increased demand of feedstock for biorefinery. In addition to consideration of production of product, the end-of-life treatment is relevant since methane emission from land can offset the benefit of carbon neutral bio products. In LCA model, it is also necessary to include indicators which represents the impact from waste treatment, ecotoxicity and human toxicity [4].

4.2 Standard and guidelines

Even though by following the well-defined guidelines and similar impact categories, the inconsistent application of it gives different LCA results [41]. In order to avoid such situation, it is necessary to follow the ISO 14040 standards and the US-EPA (US-Environmental Protection

Agency) LCA principles and practices [42]. It also includes the use of wide range of relevant impact categories which ensures the real impact shows in the results.

A generally followed method consist of four interrelated steps that are presented in Fig. 1 [43]

The structure of LCA study and demand of relevant data on energy and mass are described and fixed by DIN/ISO 14040-14043 standards. According to standards, following four steps needs to be followed during life cycle assessment [43] [44].

- Definition of the goal and the scope
- Inventory analysis
- Impact assessment
- Interpretation

Under the task of LCA study, the first step is to determine the aim of the study and the survey framework based on available data such as material and energy streams of products, processes or services. The aim of the LCA and defined system boundaries shapes the entire analysis by setting purpose such as assessment of single or multiproduct process, selection of functional unit to interpret results on similar scale, allocation method in case of multiproduct process, requirement of data to perform LCA etc [43] [44].

The second step being inventory analysis, deals with the identification of inputs and outputs of energy and of material streams for all categories of streams such as products, coproducts, intermediates and wastes. This step is realized by initiating development of flow diagram based on system boundaries which decides internal and external flow of whole scheme. The quality of a life cycle analysis is based on the quality of data collected in this phase. Thus, this is the most important step and highly time-consuming step of the life cycle analysis [43] [44].

The third step of LCA consists of activities related to the evaluation of the material and energy flows raised in the inventory analysis step. The material and energy flows determine the impact dedicated to certain environmental categories. Thus, the impact assessment summarizes and quantifies the potential environmental impact of the system under consideration. In the framework of classification of impact to environment, certain impact categories are included in LCA. The impact categories are

- Global warming potential (GWP)
- Ozone depletion potential (ODP)
- Acidification potential (AP)
- Eutrophication potential (NP)
- Human toxicity potential (HTP)
- Ecotoxicity (ETP)
- Land use

Life cycle interpretation, the fourth step of the LCA study, is engaged with the evaluation of impact assessment results generated during the second and third stage of the LCA study. This exercise provides insights into the limitations of the processes in terms of environmental performances which can be used to make conclusions and further turn into recommendations to improve environmental foot print of the system that is considered in the goal and scope of life cycle assessment [43] [44].

Figure 1: Method of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [43]

4.3 Estimation of missing data

In case of lack of real-world data, use of reference data, default optimization potentials and relevant scale-up mechanisms can be applied for environmental assessment and thus, for first hot-spot screening. For the modelling of feedstock cultivation, the focus should be on emissions from pesticides, nutrients and the use of water and land. For addressing geographic differentiation, chemical emission and resource use; the inventory modelling is required. For production efficiency, specific data should be available for the studied system and upscaling [4].

5 CONCLUSION

This paper highlights the basics of biorefinery classification and the processes involved to convert biomass into valuable products. As the expected outcome from biorefinery is to produce bio-based products in a sustainable way and create a positive impact by replacing fossil-based chemicals, the importance of requirement of framework (Including feedstock generation, processes of biorefinery and product usage) for sustainable assessment of biorefinery is explained. By following the framework of sustainable assessment, certain tools are required to perform multi-criteria assessment. Those tools are categorised as monetary tools (about the economics of production and benefits/losses), biophysical tools (about the material flows of processes) and indicator tools (estimate the socio-economic performance like employment, environmental performance). In addition to this, the method of life cycle assessment along with considerations for relevant impact categories for a particular system, the importance of the use of consistent methods/guidelines that can help in decision making on sustainability assessment of various scenarios are mentioned.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] 'H. C. Godfray, J. Beddington, I. Crute, L. Haddad, D. Lawrence, J. Muir, J. Pretty, S. Robinson, S. Thomas and C. Toulmin, "Food Security: The Challenge of Feeding 9 Billion People," *Science*, vol. 327, no. 5967, 2010'.
- [2] A. C. Caputo, M. Palumbo, P. M. Pelagagge, and F. Scacchia, 'Economics of biomass energy utilization in combustion and gasification plants: effects of logistic variables', *Biomass Bioenergy*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 35–51, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2004.04.009.
- [3] 'A. E. Turcios, A. Cayenne, H. U. and J. Papenbrock, "Halophyte Plants and Their Residues as Feedstock for Biogas Production - Chances and Challenges," *MDPI : applied science*, 2021.'
- [4] Ó. Ögmundarson, M. J. Herrgård, J. Forster, M. Z. Hauschild, and P. Fantke, 'Addressing environmental sustainability of biochemicals', *Nat. Sustain.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 167–174, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41893-019-0442-8.
- [5] F. Cherubini and S. Ulgiati, 'Crop residues as raw materials for biorefinery systems – A LCA case study', *Appl. Energy*, vol. 87, no. 1, pp. 47–57, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.08.024.
- [6] H. R. Ghatak, 'Biorefineries from the perspective of sustainability: Feedstocks, products, and processes', *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 4042–4052, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2011.07.034.
- [7] G. Rødsrud, M. Lersch, and A. Sjöde, 'History and future of world's most advanced biorefinery in operation', *Biomass Bioenergy*, vol. 46, pp. 46–59, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2012.03.028.
- [8] R. van Ree and B. Annevelink, 'Status Report Biorefinery 2007', p. 110, 2007.
- [9] F. Cherubini, 'The biorefinery concept: Using biomass instead of oil for producing energy and chemicals', *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 1412–1421, Jul. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2010.01.015.
- [10] F. Carvalheiro, L. C. Duarte, and F. M. Gírio, 'Hemicellulose biorefineries: a review on biomass pre-treatments', vol. 67, p. 17, 2008.
- [11] B. E. Dale, 'Greening? the chemical industry: research and development priorities for biobased industrial products', *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, vol. 78, no. 10, pp. 1093–1103, Oct. 2003, doi: 10.1002/jctb.850.
- [12] B. Kamm and M. Kamm, 'Principles of biorefineries', *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 137–145, Apr. 2004, doi: 10.1007/s00253-003-1537-7.
- [13] S. K. Hoekman, 'Biofuels in the U.S. – Challenges and Opportunities', *Renew. Energy*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 14–22, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2008.04.030.
- [14] 'Bohlmann GM. Process economic considerations for production of ethanol from biomass feedstocks. *Industrial Biotechnology*. 2006;2:14-20'.
- [15] J. R. Hess, C. T. Wright, and K. L. Kenney, 'Cellulosic biomass feedstocks and logistics for ethanol production', *Biofuels Bioprod. Biorefining*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 181–190, Nov. 2007, doi: 10.1002/bbb.26.
- [16] 'Galbe, M., Zacchi, G. (2007). Pre-treatment of Lignocellulosic Materials for Efficient Bioethanol Production. In: Olsson, L. (eds) *Biofuels. Advances in Biochemical Engineering/Biotechnology*, vol 108. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/10_2007_070'.
- [17] T. M. Carole, J. Pellegrino, and M. D. Paster, 'Opportunities in the industrial biobased products industry', *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, vol. 113, p. 15, 2004.
- [18] C. Cristina, P. Lucia, S. Sara, S. Francesco, D. Nobile Matteo Alessandro, and C. Amalia, 'Study of the Efficacy of Two Extraction Techniques from *Crithmum maritimum* and *Salicornia europaea*', *J.*

- Food Nutr. Res., vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 456–463, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.12691/jfnr-6-7-6.
- [19] 'European Commission. Accelerating the Development of the Market for Bio-based Products in Europe. Report of the European Commission Taskforce on Bio-Based Products: European Commission; 2007. p. 1-24.'
- [20] 'IEA. Bio-based Chemicals Value Added Products from Biorefineries. 2011. p. 1-36.'
- [21] M. FitzPatrick, P. Champagne, M. F. Cunningham, and R. A. Whitney, 'A biorefinery processing perspective: Treatment of lignocellulosic materials for the production of value-added products', *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 101, no. 23, pp. 8915–8922, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2010.06.125.
- [22] 'Galbe M, Sassner P, Wingren A, Zacchi G. Process engineering economics of bioethanol production. *Adv Biochem Eng Biotechnol.* 2007;108:303-27. doi: 10.1007/10_2007_063. PMID: 17541520.'
- [23] 'Zhang YP. Reviving the carbohydrate economy via multi-product lignocellulose biorefineries. *J Ind Microbial Biotechnol.* 2008 May;35(5):367-375. doi: 10.1007/s10295-007-0293-6. Epub 2008 Jan 8. PMID: 18180967.'
- [24] A. Alemdar and M. Sain, 'Isolation and characterization of nanofibers from agricultural residues – Wheat straw and soy hulls', *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 99, no. 6, pp. 1664–1671, Apr. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2007.04.029.
- [25] 'Sierra R, Granda C, Holtzaple MT. Short-term lime pre-treatment of poplar wood. *Bioethanol Prog.* 2009 Mar-Apr;25(2):323-32. doi: 10.1002/btpr.83. PMID: 19291802.'
- [26] 'Kamm B, Kamm M, Schmidt M, Hirth T, Schulze M. Lignocellulose-based Chemical Products and Product Family Trees. *Biorefineries-Industrial Processes and Products: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH; 2008. p. 97-149.'*
- [27] 'Kim TH, Kim JS, Sunwoo C, Lee YY. Pre-treatment of corn stover by aqueous ammonia. *Bioresour. Technol.* 2003;90:39-47'.
- [28] M. L. Rabinovich, 'WOOD HYDROLYSIS INDUSTRY IN THE SOVIET UNION AND RUSSIA: A MINI-REVIEW', p. 14.
- [29] 'Zakzeski J, Bruijninx PC, Jongerius AL, Weckhuysen BM. The catalytic valorisation of lignin for the production of renewable chemicals. *Chemical Reviews.* 2010;110:3552-99'.
- [30] 'Berlin A, Balakshin MY, Ma R, Maximenko GV, Ortiz D. Organosolv process. In: Ltd. LI, editor.: Google Patents; 2013.'
- [31] J. Holladay, J. White, J. Bozell, and D. Johnson, 'Top Value-Added Chemicals from Biomass - Volume II—Results of Screening for Potential Candidates from Biorefinery Lignin', p. 87.
- [32] 'Laurent A, Bakas I, Clavreul J, Bernstad A, Niero M, Gentil E, Hauschild MZ, Christensen TH. Review of LCA studies of solid waste management systems--part I: lessons learned and perspectives. *Waste Manag.* 2014 Mar;34(3):573-88. doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2013.10.045. Epub 2013 Dec 25. PMID: 24369845.'
- [33] 'Løken, Espen, (2007), Use of multicriteria decision analysis methods for energy planning problems, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews,* 11, issue 7, p.1584-1595, <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:eee:rensus:v:11:y:2007:i:7:p:1584-1595>.'
- [34] N. E. S. Jr, W. Yuan, M. R. Eden, B. Aksoy, and H. T. Cullinan, 'Optimal biorefinery product allocation by combining process and economic modelling', *N E,* p. 9, 2008.
- [35] 'Gasparatos A, Scolobig A. Choosing the most appropriate sustainability assessment tool. *Ecological Economics.* 2012;80:1-7.'
- [36] 'Srinivasan RS, Braham WW, Campbell DE, Curcija DC. 2011. Sustainability assessment fra.pdf'
- [37] Hanley N, Spash CL. *Cost-benefit analysis and the environment: Edward Elgar Cheltenham; 1993.*
- [38] J. Bebbington, J. Brown, and B. Frame, 'Accounting technologies and sustainability assessment models', *Ecol. Econ.*, vol. 61, no. 2–3, pp. 224–236, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.10.021.
- [39] 'Haberl H, Fischer-Kowalski M, Krausmann F, Weisz H, Winiwarter V. Progress towards sustainability? What the conceptual framework of material and energy flow accounting (MEFA) can offer. *Land Use Policy.* 2004;21:199-213'.
- [40] L. Cherchye et al., 'Creating composite indicators with DEA and robustness analysis: the case of the Technology Achievement Index', *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 239–251, Feb. 2008, doi: 10.1057/palgrave.jors.2602445.
- [41] G. Thomassen, M. Van Dael, B. Lemmens, and S. Van Passel, 'A review of the sustainability of algal-based biorefineries: Towards an integrated assessment framework', *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 68, pp. 876–887, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.02.015.
- [42] R. E. Horne, T. Grant, and K. Verghese, *Life Cycle Assessment: Principles, Practice and Prospects.* CSIRO Publishing, 2009. doi: 10.1071/9780643097964.
- [43] UNEP, Ed., *Evaluation of environmental impacts of life cycle assessment: meeting report; Brussels, 29 - 30 November 1998, and Brighton, 25 - 26 May 2000.* New York: United Nations, 2003.
- [44] 'Evert Nieuwlaar, *Life Cycle Assessment and Energy Systems,* Editor(s): Cutler J. Cleveland, *Encyclopaedia of Energy,* Elsevier, 2004, Pages 647-654, ISBN 9780121764807':

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Grant Agreement No. 862834. Any results of this project reflect only this consortium's view and the European Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

